

Nonverbal Expression of Emotions in Conflict Escalation

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Abstract—The purpose of this study is to explore how the emotions at the moment of conflict escalation are expressed nonverbally and how it can be detected by the parties involved in the conflicting situation. The study consists of two parts, in the first part it starts with the definition of “conflict” and “nonverbal communication”. Further it includes the analysis of emotions and types of emotions, which may bring to the conflict escalation. Four types of emotions and emotion constructs are analyzed, particularly fear, anger, guilt and frustration. The second part of the study analyses the general role of nonverbal behavior in interaction and communication, which information it may give during communication to the person, who sends or receives those signals. The study finishes with the analysis of the nonverbal expression of analyzed emotions and on how it can be used during interaction.

Keywords—Conflict Escalation, Emotions, Nonverbal communication,

I. INTRODUCTION

RESEARCH Research on conflict escalation and conflict management shows that conflict has several meanings depending on the situation and can be not only negative but also positive. The way individuals manage interpersonal conflicts was in the attention of researchers for a long time, during which different approaches and strategies have been developed. In this regard, there are several behaviors that bring individuals to success in interpersonal conflicts: it can be tactical plan to solve the conflict as well as understanding each other's needs and preferred outcomes [8]. According to the Lewick et al. conflict can be considered as interaction of people, depending from each other, who has incompatible goals and depend on each other in achieving those goals [29]. According to Barki and Hartwick conflict is a dynamic process between parties depending on each other, because of experienced negative emotional reactions based on unattained agreement and interference with the reaching of their goals [4]. Conflict also has been defined as the different views and incompatible goals as well as personal differences between the groups or individuals [12].

Often, conflict occurs as an interpersonal phenomenon between two interdependent parties engaged in a joint activity. These very characteristics of jointness and interdependence make conflict a mixed-motive situation in which parties involved are faced with a tension between motives to compete and cooperate [28].

Thus, the situation can be considered as conflicting when we believe that the aims of the other party can not be reached in a collaborative way [42]. Nevertheless, conflict is not only about the different goals, but different approaches to the issue, as in some situations parties may have the same goal and different approaches to the issue, and as a result of these different approaches they may face conflicting situations among themselves.

Conflict can be defined also as incompatible activities, when the actions of one person obstruct the actions of another person [13]. The incompatibility of activities can be observed as in cooperative, as well as in competitive approaches. Nevertheless, the expectations and outcomes of the conflict very much depends on the way people approach situation, which leads to the conflict escalation. Thus many researchers underline, that the cooperative approach to the situation captures many benefits of conflict and cooperative approach is the basis for constructive conflict management, despite existing incompatibility of activities.

Conflict can be defined also as the situation with different goals and different interests, that destroy effective choices as parties involved frame conflict without multilateral assessment of the situation and without completely dealing with the conflict. And therefore they easily come to the conclusion that they not only have incompatible goals but also incompatible approaches to the conflict. This accent on the opposing interests and competitive approach can be destroying for negotiating the conflict, as competitive approach is considered to be more difficult to reverse while cooperative approach can be easier to revert to competition [13].

Despite the fact, that different approaches, conflicting activities and incompatible goals are the key factors in conflict escalation, conflict escalates also because of emotions people feel. In this regard, conflict is also defined as the emotions people feel during certain situation, that lead to conflict escalation. The conflicting situations that are created based on the emotions, relationships or values are mostly considered as destructive conflicts. The stronger emotions felt or relationships the more destructive will be conflict with long-term negative consequences [12].

Thus, the choices people take in certain situations may lead to the conflict escalation or lead to more constructive problem solution. They can manage their emotions, which can lead to effective or ineffective conflict management [2]. Nevertheless, there are types of conflicts that are more difficult in general to make effective choices in order to prevent the conflict. The most important in these situations are the choices the participants make or the skills they use to implement them. People control the situation and conflict, therefore effective

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ways to control conflict productively is much easier through the combination of efforts from the all sides involved in the conflict.

The most critical part in approaching the conflicting situation depends on how people understand and frame the conflict, i.e. if they see themselves in the conflict, their emotions, the issues on the stake etc. Very often parties involved in the situation are angry about the others for their incompatible actions, but they never think that the incompatible actions of the other parties are not intended to frustrate them [2].

II. DEFINING 'NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION': THEORETICAL OVERVIEW

The study of nonverbal communication is recent. The importance of non verbal communication has been well established only during the second decade of the 20th century. The first researchers who recognized the need to examine verbal and nonverbal behavior with each other to fully understand the dynamics of interaction process were Birdwhistell [1952, 1970] and Hall [1959] [40:32]. In more recent research nonverbal communication issues has been developed by many researchers in the field of Intercultural communication, Business management, Behavior Studies, etc.

The theory and research associated with nonverbal communication focuses on three primary units: the communication environment [physical and spatial], the communicator's physical characteristics and the body movements and positions [gestures, posture, touching, facial expressions, eye behavior and vocal behavior] [27:24].

Physical environment and site can contribute to the tone and mood of people [33]. The rooms can be bright colored with overstuffed chairs, soft lighting and artwork create more relaxed environment, by creating an affable mood, which can be helpful in order to act more cooperatively. The location can also cause some feelings and emotions, which can lead to the advantage of one side. Even the furniture in the rooms can be used to communicate power and status [29: 47]. Seats, space and seating positions can also determine one's role in the group. For example, cooperatively oriented parties tend to seat side by side, while competitively oriented parties prefer to seat across from one another [27:117]. The use of personal space also can be the clue to discover the intentions and strategies of opponents [27:115]. Face expressions and body language, i.e. kinesics [7] can also be the important source of information. Face expressions are the first source of emotions people feel [16], consequently, if negotiators feel any emotions, like anger, boredom, etc, it will appear on face and on gestures and postures. In general, most important, emotional messages during the communication process and conflict escalation may be expressed by nonverbal signals [24].

Kinesics has a tremendous impact on the communication process. Kendon et al. argue that everything counts during the communication: the time of the communication process [morning, lunch time, late in the evening], the table [round, square], the lights [white, in the middle of the room], the use of microphones, the breaks, the phone calls, the space between the chairs, the way the negotiators dress, and so on. Everything

is important. Nierenberg emphasizes that the slight movement of an eyebrow, the tilt of the head, the sudden movement of the hand - all are messages that an individual who deals with people must understand and continue to study. Thus, nonverbal communication can be defined as «communication without words through communicating channels» [47:5].

Nonverbal communication can be used to highlight, complement, contradict and regulate the semantics of verbal messages. Friesen and Ekman in 1969 proposed five major categories of nonverbal behavior, particularly kinesics, that illustrate some of these functions, such as emblem, illustrator, regulator, adaptor and affect display.

Emblems refer to the small class of non-verbal acts that can be accurately translated into words [handshake, shaking a fist at someone, a smile, a frown]. Illustrators, the second category, are very much a part of speech and serve the function of emphasis [head and hand movements that occur more frequently with primary-stressed words, pointing gestures or other movements that redundantly draw a picture of the linguistic referent. Included in this category are those movements that seem to serve as added punctuation or emphases, such as pointing with the hand or with the turn of the head, or tracking the contour of an object or person referred to verbally. If a person wants to convey the idea that what he is saying is important, he will use movements with his speech to get more information across.

The third major category, affect display, deals with happiness, anger, surprise, fear, disgust. Regulators refer to acts that help to initiate and determine the speech of participants in a social situation. These regulators might suggest to a speaker that he keep talking, that he clarify, or that he hurry up and finish. The fifth category, adaptors, refer to acts that are related to the satisfaction of bodily needs, such as moving into a more comfortable position or scratching [14].

Later all these 5 categories were complemented also with 'contradiction', by M.Lustig [31]. Contradictions can occur when one gives positive verbal reply while using a negative gesture or posture at the same time. These contradictions show that someone is amiss or they can indicate an attempt on deception. The less evaluative interpretation might simply be that the verbal message is not all in accordance with what the person wants to convey. In intercultural communication these incongruities, when they occur, might serve as a signal from sender to receiver, that something is wrong [31]. Allan Pease among other gestures and postures mentions also contradicting gestures, for example if a man rubs his eye and looks towards the floor with eyebrows raised to the disbelief position and his head is turned away and down, but he is smiling, on the one hand can be seen as everything is ok, but this is the classical gesture of deceit [38].

III. EMOTIONS IN CONFLICT ESCALATION

Emotions are the general phenomenon of human functioning. Emotions are "complex, episodic, dynamic and structured" [20:12] The complexity of emotion can be explained in the way, that it involves "episodes of emotional experience, including perceptions, thoughts, different feelings, bodily changes, dispositions to experience further emotional

episodes to have further thoughts and feelings, and to behave in certain way” [20:13] The episodic and dynamic character of emotions can be explained in the way that they depend on different factors, including the way in which the episodes and dispositions interweave and interact with each other and with other aspects of the persons life. The notion of emotional episode is usually longer than the notion of emotion itself [1]. And an emotion is structured in that it constitutes part of a narrative—roughly, an unfolding sequence of actions and events, thoughts and feelings—in which the emotion itself is embedded. The actions which we do out of an emotion, and the various ways of expressing an emotion, are also seen as part of the same narrative, but not themselves as part of the emotion itself [20]. Emotions are the basic phenomenon of human interaction, they help to inform others about one’s internal states and behavioral intentions [37].

Emotions can and often do being very quickly, and very often our conscious self does not participate in or even witness what in our mind triggers an emotion at any particular moment. Each emotion has unique signals, the most identifiable being in the face and the voice. With the ability to identify emotions early on, we may be better able to deal with people in a variety of situations and to manage our own emotional responses to their feelings. We don’t become emotional about everything, we are not in the grip of emotions all the time. Emotions come and go. We may feel an emotion one moment and may not feel any emotion at another moment. The most common moment in which emotions occur, is when we sense, rightly or wrongly, that something that seriously affects our welfare, for better or worse, is happening or about to happen. Emotions evolved to prepare us to deal quickly with the most vital events in our lives. Emotions begin so quickly, that we are not aware of the processes in our mind that set them off [16].

Emotions and behavior are closely connected, emotions despite other functions, first of all monitor our inner world, our relationships with outer world and help us to act [30:272]. As was mentioned before, emotions occur very quickly and its hard to control them, especially if an emotion is very strong and as we behave based on the emotions we feel, emotions cause conflict, as well solve them. Emotions can be hot or cold and automatic or controlled. Hot emotions belong to “go” system and cool ones belong to “know” system, where “know” system is more complex, slow, strategic, coherent. The hot system is impulsive and hastily reactive and undermines rational attempts at self-control. [30:274].

The theory of emotional competence is focused on emotional behavior of people and an ability to control emotions and consequently to control behaviour. In a more specific definition, emotional competence can be defined as the capacity to articulate and manage the emotion-related abilities an individual needs to deal with relational problems raised in a variable and challenging social environment [43]. This can serve as a compass for negotiators and mediators to find an orientation into the ideology and morality of the counterparts. It can be easier to solve conflicts if one can understand its emotions. If one can not understand its own emotions, they can not understand the emotions of other

people. The emotional process may be considered as a predisposition to action: the emotion if recognized brings with it the awareness of being a protagonist of our own actions.

Emotional competence could be satisfied in mastering emotional communication in conflict interaction, because emotions typically arise in the evaluations of events in relation to a person’s individual concerns and expectations [21]. Very often in an communication process negative emotions arise from interpretation of the counterpart’s actions rather than from an objective appraisal of their actions. Then in this case the conflict may be created either from a lack of knowledge, or wrong assessment of the actions of the other side. Despite the fact, that in order to hide, disguise and modulate feelings, there are techniques such as how to be accepted, to communicate, to protect oneself, to save face, etc [43].

Starting with fear, as a negative emotion, that can bring to conflict escalation, its necessary to mention that fear can lead people to “flight” or to an avoidance of conflict, as well as to “fight” or counter phobic aggressive response, or to a desire to avoid disaster by reaching an agreement [30]. In case of fear the “go” system, which was mentioned before, represents a double edged sword.

Strong fear brings to the anger, one of the strong emotions in emotional system of humankind. Very often anger can lead to hostility and sometimes even bring to revenge. To understand why, its necessary to mention, that our brains does three things: maps a comprehensive representation of the thing, animal or person who hurts us, maps the state of our body [for example readiness to fight] and maps kind of relationship we have to the perpetrator and how we might respond [30:275]. Thus, anger is more complex, than fear. We get angry when we believe that other person treats us with disrespect and the more is hurt the more is anger. We feel anger, when we see, that th person, who hurts us, has a control over the situation and we want to harm others, we become very hostile, when we believe, that they could avoid hurting us. As Paul Ekman describes “each emotion has a mood saturated with that emotion, there is also a personality train, in which each emotion plays a central role. In anger that trait is hostility” [16:143].

Very often strong anger can lead to humiliation. Humiliation involves, putting and holding down and rendering the other helpless to resist the debasement. We feel humiliated, when we are unable to resist the debasement and deem it to be illegitimate and unwanted. What counts as humiliation is different from one historical period to another, from one culture to another and from one person to another. Feeling of humiliation can be the cause of strong emotions, that can have destructive consequences not only for the ones, that were felt humiliated, but also for the others. Humiliation, can lead to the feelings of revenge and to collective regression. As Lindner suggests “considering of humiliation can explain the violence and terrorism more than other explanations. Feeling of humiliation may trigger narcissistic rage and acts of aggression meant to lessen pain and increase self-worth. When publicly humiliated, may instigate mass destruction and war [30:280].

Guilt is elaborated emotion and elaborated emotions are very culturally dependent. In its simplest description, guilt may

be understood as an affective state of regret at having done something one believes one should not have done. Humiliation, humility, shame and guilt are related concepts. Being able to feel shame is prosaically, as is the ability to feel guilt. Guilt can be abused, however, as a tool of social control, because guilty people feel less deserving and are less likely to assert their rights and prerogatives. Feelings of guilt can prevent people from doing evil [30].

Feeling of guilt for past omissions and transgressions, if acknowledged, remedied by apology and forgiveness, can be a powerful healing force in conflict. What is needed for shame and guilt is to be healing force is the courage to face them and gauge them with candidness, humility and warmth. If not acknowledged and worked through constructively, feelings of shame and guilt can help maintain destructive conflict. In turn, conflict can impinge on feelings of guilt. Feelings of guilt can be pushed toward violence if conditions inhibit their acknowledgement and healing. Moreover deliberately creating "pathological guilt" by making opponents in a conflict or communication, feel guilty. So as to weaken them may rather undermine long-term constructive solutions, successful communication or solutions to conflict depend on firm commitments from strong players. Guilt can best be borne to healing, if embedded in respectful restorative justice.

Amongst the emotions felt in different situations, there are four types of emotions that are considered to be conflict relevant: anger and frustration, shame and guilt, fear and sadness.

Hostility is an emotion construct or mood [16] that involves anger, anxiety and frustration. These types of emotions are more self focused and arise as reaction to threats or failure to achieve one's desires or goals and usually they motivate people to affirm or assert aspects of their independent self. As for anger, it has been distinguished to be connected more to an approach, people take to the situation, than to behavior. Moreover, anger has found to be connected more to impulsive approach and aggressive thoughts, that can be expressed in attacking other person with an intention to harm and insult other person [41].

Frijda also finds that anger is related to antagonism and the goal of conquering or at least setting the self against an obstacle or difficulty [18].

While hostility is self-asserting or protective, the self-conscious emotion construct reflects a different type of concern about the self. Shame, guilt, embarrassment and humiliation focus primarily on a negative, self-conscious and self evaluative view of the self, and tend to be associated with conciliatory and compliant behaviors [5]. Shame can be related to an attempt to apologize and guilt to a desire to be forgiven [41]. Sadness is a long-lasting emotion.

Fear can be considered as a social emotion with a focus on the other party and characterized by the apprehension related to troubling or hurting the other party [26]. This fear reflects the joint, interdependent and social nature of conflict. Roseman and his colleagues [41] found fear to be related to an increased attention to danger, ruminations about worst outcomes, and a desire to run away.

IV. NONVERBAL EXPRESSION OF EMOTIONS IN CONFLICT ESCALATION

The study of body language was first used in 1970th, by Ekman and Freisen. Before it was the study of kinesics, which was developed by Ray Birdwhistell. Kinesics is the interpretation of body language such as facial expressions and gestures - or, more formally, non-verbal behavior related to movement, either of any part of the body or the body as a whole. The movements considered to be 'systematic', i.e. a system with a structure that can be described independently of the behavior of particular participants. Where the structure of body motion communication behavior must be described in a way which allows us to measure the significance of particular motions or complexes of motions to communicational processes [7:77]. Nevertheless, an idea, that tried to develop Birdwhistell, never fulfilled the promise that was claimed, yet the idea that gestural expression is culturally patterned and not something that is 'universal' came to be widely accepted, and the concept of kinesics was very important in bringing about the systematic analysis of bodily action from a communicative point of view.

The concept later was developed by Ekman and Freisen [14], but in comparison to Birdwhistell, who looked at kinesics from linguistic point of view, Ekman and Freisen, have built the concept of kinesics from psychological point of view, putting emotion as the central point of kinesics.

Whatever we feel is expressed by our nonverbal behavior. When we feel negative emotions, we send negative nonverbal messages and in case of positive emotions, nonverbal messages are positive. When emotions are aroused, changes on the face and body occur automatically without choice or deliberation. These changes begin in a split second, people don't actively select when they will feel an emotion. Instead they usually experience emotions more passively as happening to them, and in the case of negative emotions such as fear or anger, it may happen to them despite themselves. Not only is there little choice about when an emotion is felt, but people often don't feel they have much choice about whether or not the expressive signs of the emotion are manifest to others. In order to understand what people feel during communication process and in terms of negative emotions, to reduce them, one must understand nonverbal signals and their meanings.

The way we experience emotions can be very complex. We may rapidly experience several emotions one after another or to feel several emotions at once. There are four basic nonverbal expression of emotional existence that will be considered in this study. These are negative emotions, that may be the dominant ones during conflict escalation.

Sadness is one of the longer-lasting emotions. Sadness and agony in facial and vocal expressions call for help from others. These expressions are involuntary, not deliberate, but one of their evolutionary functions is to cause others who see the expressions to feel concern and want to offer comfort, each expression conveys a set of related messages. The messages for sadness and agony revolve around "I am suffering; comfort and help me." Furthermore, as we are constructed to respond with emotion to emotion; we usually feel the message. That

does not always mean we feel the emotion that is being signaled to us.

Sadness on the face can be expressed on the upper and lower face. One of the strong and reliable signs are the angling upward of the inner corners of the eyebrows. It is reliable because few people can make this movement voluntarily, so it could rarely be deliberately fabricated. Even when people are attempting not to show how they are feeling, these obliquely positioned eyebrows will often leak their sadness. Moreover, in most people a vertical wrinkle between the brows will appear, when the eyebrows are drawn up and together. In some people that wrinkle is permanently etched in the face, and if that is so it will deepen and darken when the inner corners of the eyebrows are pulled up and together. As for the lower face, lips usually are stretched horizontally, pushed up. Raised cheeks, which are another part of the full display of this intense feeling, also signal the deep sadness. And finally the skin between the tip of the chin and lower lip may be wrinkled and pushed upward, by the action of chin muscle [16:99].

In the slight sadness the lip corners can be pulled downward, the stronger the sadness the stronger will be the expression. When this expression is without eyebrows pulled upward, this may be the sign of the limitation of revealed sadness. If the lips are pulled down strongly, without the action of eyebrows or eyes, it can be the sign of disbelief or negation, the movement that some people do as a symbol [16:105].

One of the important and highly reliable signs of sadness are eyebrows. The lip corners are the another very reliable sign of sadness, when they are pulled down. When lip corners are pulled down and the lower lip is pushed up it can be the sign of uncertainty, like a shrug with hands. When the lower lip is pushed up and pressed, it is the sign of determination or concentration.

Sometimes people may feel several emotions at the same time, or emotions can change one another in seconds, in this case one could see the messages of two emotions at the same time, for example sadness in combination with surprise, happiness or fear. When we see combination of sadness and fear, it can be expressed by raised inner corners of eyebrows, as a sign of sadness and wide-open eyes, as a sign of surprise. This expression can occur when one feels recollection of the happy moments in the past, but the person becomes sad, because those moments are in the past [16:109].

One of the most dangerous emotions is anger. Anger can arouse in the situations of physical or psychological insult, it can also appear in a failure of memory or ability, in a disappointment from the actions of the other people, as was mentioned before. Anger is very dangerous, because it calls forth anger, which leads to conflict escalation. Different reasons of the anger don't arouse the same type or intensity of anger. The word anger covers different related experiences from slight annoyance to rage. Thus there is not only the difference in the strength of angry feelings but the difference in the kind of anger felt. As Paul Ekman defines: "indignation is self-righteous anger; sulking is a passive anger; exasperation refers to having one's patience tried excessively. Revenge is a type of angry action usually committed after a period of

reflection about the offence, sometimes of greater intensity than the act that provoked it" [16:118].

We differ from each other in the way we experience emotions. There are people, who doesn't have the capacity for extreme anger, while they are people, who becomes angry very often. Different expressions of anger, depends on how intensive was the emotion and it is not the same way for everyone. When we feel intense anger, very often we are not aware of it, even when we do angry actions, send angry verbal and nonverbal messages. Thus, in order to control anger, as was mentioned in previous chapter, one must "regulate or suppress its reactions, reevaluate the situation and plan the actions in order to remove the source of our anger" [16:124]. Anger informs others about dissatisfaction or trouble and has its signals on the face and voice. The signals tell the person, who is the source of our anger, that whatever he or she is doing is objectionable.

As each emotion has its mood, the mood for anger is hostility [16:126]. Thus, when anger lasts too long, the person, who feels anger shows hostile attitude to the person, who makes him angry.

As have been mentioned, signals of anger can be seen on the face and voice. The signals on the face can be seen on upper face as well as on the lower face. The signals on the upper face can be found on the eyelids and eyebrows. The lower and upper eyelids become tightened, which signals the controlled anger or slight annoyance. It can also occur, when the person tries to focus on something, to concentrate. As for eyebrows, they can be drawn together, which also signals that person is concentrating or finding something difficult. When there is the combination of tightened eyelids and lowered, drawn together eyebrows, that is the signals of controlled or very slight anger, as well as perplexity or concentration. When there is the combination of signs, like lowered and drawn together eyebrows, tensed lower eyelids and raised upper eyelids, this is the sign of anger.

As for lower face, the jaw is often thrust forward, sometimes the lips are pressed. When lips are pressed with tensed lower eyelids, it is the sign of slight anger or anger, that just begins, if the lips are just pressed, for some people it shows just thinking about something, or can be the sign of mannerism.

The message of controlled anger or resignation can be sent in the form of pressed lips together in combination with lower lip pushed up. There are also some people who make this expression while thinking and in other people it can be the sign of mannerism. Thus, the anger on the lower face can be seen in the narrowed and pressed lips, where the upper lip is raised and the lower lip is lowered [16:133].

Compare to surprise, fear lasts longer. Fear appears, when we feel the threat of physical or psychological harm. People can learn to be afraid of everything and we can act very different when we are afraid, we can do anything or nothing depending on the situation. When we can not do anything with the fear we feel, we may become angry at whatever causes the fear, we may also be angry on ourselves, or even feel disgust for becoming afraid, if we think that we could control the situation without fear.

Thus, each emotion has its mood. For sadness it is blue mood, for anger it is irritable mood, for fear it is anxiety – mood when we worry about the situation. People, who become mostly in blue mood, are melancholic personalities, depression related to sadness-agony, people in irritable mood are hostile personalities, fear has anxious moods, shy or timid personalities. Such people are preoccupied with how they may fail to deal with social situations, they have low self esteem and avoid social contact.

The facial messages that can be sent during the fear can be seen at upper face and lower face. On the upper face it appears in the eyes and brows. If the eyes are opened wide it can be the sign of fear as well as surprise. If the eye widening happens for one or two seconds, it can be surprise, if it lasts longer, then it is fear. When tensed lower eyelids accompany raised upper eyelids and the rest of the face is blank, it is the sign of fear. This message can be sent in terror, when the person doesn't want to show the emotions felt.

As for eyebrows, when they are raised, without wide opened eyes, it is emphasis sign. When someone is talking, they do this sign while accenting a word, the level of the voice can be louder in this case as well. It also can be sign of disbelief, when listener shows it, while the other person speaks. It can be the sign of surprise, when the upper eyelids are raised as well. In surprise upper eyelids would be raised and lower eyelids would not be tensed, while in the fear the upper eyelids are raised and the lower eyelids are tensed. As for lower face in fear lips are stretched back toward the eyes.

As for disgust, it can be described in many ways, depending on the context [taste, smell, touch, social disgust]. Disgust can be felt over the person, who doesn't fit into social order, or who unfairly criticizes others, who acts brutally or racists. Disgust has a function to remove us from what we consider objectionable.

Contempt is different from disgust. In comparison to disgust contempt can be experienced only about the actions of people. We usually feel superior to another person, when we feel contempt and those, who occupy a subordinate position, may feel contempt to their superiors. Contempt as well as disgust as other emotions can vary on intensity and strength. Disgust is negative emotion, as person doesn't feel good, when he experience disgust. Contempt will be present often with anger or annoyance, as well as without any additional emotions.

As for facial expression in the case of disgust its message on the face will be expressed in the form of raised upper lip, raised lower lip with slight protruding. The wrinkles extending from the nostrils downward to lip corners is deep. Nostril wings are raised and there are wrinkles on the both sides and bridge of the nose. Cheeks are raised and brows are lowered, but in comparison to anger, in disgust brows are not put together and the upper eyelids are not raised.

In the case of contempt we have nearly the expression stronger on the one side of face. Corners of the lips are tightened and slightly raised and it is more visible on the one side of the face.

Gestures are the movements made by some parts of body [arm and hand movements, head gestures]. The movements such as performing tasks, for example, eating, grooming,

smoking are not considered as gestures, but arm and hand movements that allude to and represent the performance, are considered as gestures. Gestures perform many functions, such as replace speech, regulate the flow and rhythm of interaction, maintain attention, add emphasis and clarity to speech, help characterize and make memorable the content of speech etc [45].

Gestures can be divided into two groups: speech independent and speech dependent. Speech independent gestures are also known as emblems [16] or autonomous gestures [25]. These are nonverbal acts that have direct verbal translation or dictionary definition. These gestures are the less depending on the speech and occur as a single gesture, independently from the speech. Gesture systems not limited to a specific task are known as sign languages. Sign language is commonly thought as a form of communication for the hearing impaired. Speech-independent gestures may be used when verbal channels are blocked or fail, but they also are used during verbal interaction. Speech-independent gestures may be used before, during or after speech [27:221]. Thus, speech-independent gestures can communicate messages without attendant speech, their meaning are still influenced by context. Giving someone 'the finger' can be humorous or insulting, depending on who is performing it and what other behaviours accompany it. Facial expressions and eye movement accompanying speech-independent gestures are likely to expand the range of possible meanings associated with a hand gesture. Moreover emblematic gestures have different meanings in different cultures, for example the thumbs up gesture means 'good', 'positive' or 'ok' in US, but in the Middle East it is an obscene gesture.

As for speech-related gestures, called also illustrators, are directly tied to or accompany speech [27:236]. The meanings and functions of these gestures are revealed through the examination of the speech. People tend to illustrate more than usual when they are furious, horrified, very agitated, distressed, or excitedly enthused. Overall there are four types of speech-related gestures [15], [24], [46]: speaker's referent-related gestures, speaker's relationship to the referent gestures, punctuation gestures, interactive gestures.

Referent related gestures are completing the meaning of the speech. Sometimes these are movements depicting concrete referents, sometimes vague, sometimes abstract ideas are the referent for gestural depiction. For example pointing movements can help to indicate specific person, place or thing being discussed. Abstract referents occur when we draw in the air the path of an idea or direction.

Punctuation gestures accent, emphasize and organize important segments, such as single word or a larger utterance unit, of the discourse. When these gestures are used to emphasize the word or phrase, they usually are accompanied by the primary voice stress. Punctuation gestures can also organize the stream of speech into units. Punctuation gestures can be accomplished with body movements other than hands.

Interactive gestures acknowledge the other interactant relative to the speaker and help regulate and organize the dialogue itself. Because they are directed at the ongoing involvement and shared roles of interactants, these gestures

occurs only in the presence of others. The main function of interactive gestures is to include the interaction partner in the dialogue. These are the pointing gestures in the partners direction. There are four groups of interactive gestures: gestures that deliver information, citing the partner, seeking response from the partner, turn gestures. Delivering gestures as a group deliver information by the speaker to the addressee (general delivery, shared information, digression gestures). Citing gesture as a group refer to the previous contribution by the addressee (general citing, acknowledgment). Seeking gestures as a group aim to elicit a specific response from the addressee (seeking help, seeking agreement, seeking following) and turn gestures refer to the issues around the speaking turn (giving turn, taking turn, turn open).

Thus, the explanation of the role and meaning of the gestures during speech can help to understand how they work together and what messages they contain. Nonverbal messages and speech are rhythmically coordinated, this means a change in one behavior will lead to the change in another behavior. Thus, as a speech units can be grouped together to form a larger units, so can movement units. Nonverbal messages that accompany verbal behavior called kinesics markers [7], that operate at several different levels, for example eye blink in the beginning and end of some words, leaning back during listening and leaning forward while talking. This called self-synchrony [25]. When there are two or more people in the conversation one can observe interaction synchrony [matching and meshing]. Interaction synchrony is tendency to mimic the mannerism, facial expressions, postures and other behavior of the people they interact with. This has been called 'chameleon effect' [10]. When the speaker's behavior elicits an offsetting or compensatory behavior from the other interaction partner this calls matching. When the listener's behavior is a mirror image of the speaker's, this form of matching is called mirroring [27]. Matching and mirroring appear during periods of more positive speech and it happens unconsciously. By this body behaviour one can say about the possible development of discussion or relationship between interactants.

Nevertheless, from time to time nonverbal behavior can contradict verbal speech. Paul Ekman calls it leakage. Very often people have not only to conceal their feelings, but also to falsify it. [15:33]. Moreover, some emotions are harder to conceal than others, as Paul Ekman states in his book (Telling Lies): terror is harder to conceal than worry. Consequently, the stronger the feeling, the harder it is to conceal it, this implies, the stronger is emotion, the easier to see it. Any emotion can be falsified to help conceal any other emotion. The smile is the mask most frequently employed. It serves as the opposite of all the negative emotions – fear, anger, distress, disgust and so on. Another reason for the popularity of the smile as a mask is that it is the easiest of the facial expressions of emotions to make voluntarily [15:36]. As for facial expression, when the person has feelings that he tries to conceal for several reason, it can be visible "in a change in the expression of the face, a movement of the body, an inflection to the voice, a swallowing in the throat, a very deep or shallow breath, long pauses between words, a slip of the tongue, a micro facial expression, a gestural slip" [15:44]. And these nonverbal signals are mostly

impossible to hide, as thoughts and feelings are involved the need to think about each word before it is spoken – weighing possibilities, searching for a word or idea – may be obvious in pauses during speech or more subtly in a tightening of the lower eyelid or eyebrow and certain changes in gesture.

Concealing the changes in face, body and voice requires a struggle. Even when the concealment is successful and there is no leakage of the feelings, sometimes the struggle itself will be noticeable. While concealing an emotion is not easy, neither is falsifying the appearance of an unfelt emotion, even when there is no other emotion that must be concealed. It requires more than just saying "im angry" or "im afraid". The deceiver must look and sound as if he is angry or afraid if his claim is to be believed. It is not easy to assemble the right movements, the particular changes in voice, that are required for falsifying emotions. There are certain movements of the face, for example, that very few people can perform voluntarily. Falsifying becomes much harder just when it is needed most to help conceal another emotion. Trying to look angry is not easy, but if fear is felt when the person tries to look angry the person will be torn. One set of impulses arising out of the fear pulls one way, while the deliberate attempt to seem angry pulls the other way. The brows, for example, are involuntarily pulled upward in fear, but to falsify anger, the person must pull them down [15:49].

There is too much to consider at once. Too many sources – words, pauses, sound of the voice, expressions, head movements, gestures, posture, respiration, flushing or blinking, sweating and so on. And all of these sources may transmit information simultaneously.

There are a number of other reasons why people pay such attention to faces. The face is the primary site for the display of emotions. Together with the voice, it may tell the listener how the speaker feels about what is being said—but not always accurately, since faces can lie about feelings. If there is difficulty hearing, watching the speaker's lips can help the listener figure out the words being spoken. Attending to the face can also provide an important signal necessary for conversations to proceed [15:83]. So, attention must be paid to the voice and body. The voice, like the face, is tied to the areas of the brain involved in emotion. It is very difficult to conceal some of the changes in voice that occur when emotion is aroused.

The body is also a good source of leakage and deception clues. Unlike the face or voice, most body movements are not directly tied to the areas of the brain involved in emotion. Monitoring of body movements need not be difficult. A person can feel and often see what his body is doing. Concealment of body movement could be much easier than concealing facial expressions or voice changes in emotion. But most people don't bother. The voice refers to everything involved in speech other than the words themselves. The most common vocal deception clues are pauses. The pauses may be too long or too frequent. Hesitating at the start of a speaking turn, particularly if the hesitation occurs when someone is responding to a question, may arouse suspicion [15:92]. Hearing how badly she sounds may make a liar more afraid of being caught, which only increases her pauses and speech errors. Probably this is

most true when the upset is a feeling of anger or fear. Changes in the voice produced by emotion are not easy to conceal. If the lie is principally about emotions felt at the very moment of the lie, then there is a good chance for leakage. If the aim of the lie was to conceal fear or anger, the voice should sound higher and louder, and the rate of talk may be faster.

Anyway, individuals differ in their emotional expressiveness. The shrug and the finger are two examples of actions that are called emblems, to distinguish them from all of the other gestures that people show. Emblems, as have been mentioned before, are almost always performed deliberately. The person who makes an emblem knows what she is doing. She has chosen to state a message. But there are exceptions. Just as there are slips of the tongue, there are slips in body movement—emblems that leak information the person is trying to conceal. There are two ways to tell that an emblem is a slip, revealing concealed information, and not a deliberate message. One is when only a fragment of the emblem is performed, not the entire action. The shrug can be performed by raising both shoulders, or by turning the palms up, or by a facial movement that involves raising the brows and dropping the upper eyelid and making a horseshoe-shaped mouth, or by combining all of these actions and, sometimes, throwing in a sideways head tilt [16:102]. When an emblem is leakage, only one element will be shown, and even it won't be complete. Only one shoulder may be raised, and not very high; or only the lower lip may be pushed up; or the palms may be turned up only slightly. Thus, any movement on the body can send the message about certain feeling.

V. CONCLUSION

Emotions change how we see the world and how we interpret the actions of others [16]. Emotions are closely connected to behavior, they not only monitor our inner world but help us to act by building relationships in the outer world. Whatever we feel is expressed by our nonverbal behavior, if we feel negative emotions our nonverbal behavior is negative and opposite.

Thus, the paper contributes to the understanding of the role of emotions and their nonverbal expression in conflict escalation. Conflict may appear when people are not able to control their emotions and can be expressed verbally as well as nonverbally. Nonverbal behavior can accompany speech, repeat, what was said verbally and conflict, complement, substitute, accent or regulate with verbal behavior and, in general, can not be interpreted separately from verbal behavior. In order to understand better and to build successful relationship and communication the ability to understand nonverbal messages may have great impact in this process. Nevertheless, only qualitative research methods were used in this study. In order to make more precise assessment quantitative data is necessary.

By exploring the link between emotions, their role in conflict escalation and their nonverbal expression, this paper may contribute to the development of the bigger research on the relation between nonverbal expression of negative emotions during conflict escalation as well as the reasons,

consequences and possible approaches to reduce conflict escalation on its very early stage.

REFERENCES

- [1] Agnes M. [2009] Theories of emotion causation: a review, *Journal of Cognition and Emotion*, vol 23, N4
- [2] Averill, J.A. [1982], *Anger and Aggression: An Essay on Emotion*, Springer-Verlag, New York,
- [3] Bacharach, S.B. and Lawler, E.J. [1981], *Bargaining: Power, Tactics and Outcomes*, Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, CA.
- [4] Barki, H. and Hartwick, J. [2004], Conceptualising the construct of interpersonal conflict, *International Journal of Conflict Management*, fVol. 15, pp. 216-44.
- [5] Barrett, K.C. [1995], *A functionalist approach to shame and guilt in Self-conscious emotions: the psychology of shame, guilt, embarrassment and pride*, New York, Guilford Press, pp.25-63
- [6] Bedjaoui M. [2001] *Conflict resolution: new approaches and methods*
- [7] Birdwhistell, R [1970], *Kinesics and Context*. University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia
- [8] Brett, J.M. [2007], *Negotiating Globally: How to Negotiate Deals, Resolve Disputes, and Make Decisions Across Cultural Boundaries*, 2nd ed, John Wiley & Sons, San Francisco, CA.
- [9] Brett, J.M., Pinkley, R.L. and Jackofsky, E.F. [1996], Alternatives to having a BATNA in dyadic negotiation: the influence of goals, self-efficacy and alternatives on negotiated outcomes, *International Journal of Conflict Management*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 121-38.
- [10] Chartrand T.L., Bargh J.A., [1999] "The Chameleon Effect: The Perception – Behavior Link and Social Interaction", *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol.26, N6
- [11] Dam S [2005]. *Aspects of non-verbal communication*
- [12] De Dreu, C.K.W. and Weingart, L.R. [2003], Task versus relationship conflict, team performance, and team member satisfaction: a meta-analysis", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88, pp. 741-9.
- [13] Deutsch M., [1973] *The Resolution of Conflict: Constructive and Destructive Processes*, Yale University Press
- [14] Ekman P. [1972], *Studies in emotion and social interaction*
- [15] Ekman P. [1997], *What the face reveals: Basic and applied studies of spontaneous expression using the facial action coding system [FACS]*;
- [16] Ekman P. [2003], *Emotions revealed: Understanding faces and feelings*
- [17] Ekman, P. [1991] *Telling lies*, Berkley Press
- [18] Frijda N.H., Kuipers P., ter Schure E., [1989] Relations among emotion, appraisal and emotional action readiness, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57
- [19] Frisen and Ekman [1969], *Non-verbal behavior*
- [20] Goldie, P. [2002]. *The emotions – a philosophical exploration*. Oxford University Press
- [21] Greenberg, L.S. [2002]. *Emotion-focused therapy: Coaching clients to work through their feelings*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association
- [22] Jehn, K.A. and Bendersky, C. [2003], Intragroup conflict in organizations: a contingency perspective on the conflict-outcome relationship", *Research in Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 25, pp. 187-242.
- [23] Kelley, H.H. and Stahelski, A.J. [1970], Social interaction basis of cooperators and competitors beliefs about others, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 16, pp. 66-91.
- [24] Kendon, A. [1981] *Nonverbal communication, interaction, and gesture : selections from Semiotica*, The Hague: Mouton, cop. 1981
- [25] Kendon, A. [2004] *Gesture: Visible Action as Utterance*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- [26] Kitayama, S., Markus, H.R., Kurokawa, M. [2000], Culture, emotions and well-being: Good feelings in Japand and the United States, *Cognition and Emotion*, 14
- [27] Knapp, M. L., Hall, J.A. [2006] *Nonverbal communication in human interaction*. NY: Holt, Rinehart & Winston. Editions
- [28] Komorita S.S., Parks C.D. [1995] *Interpersonal Relations: Mixed Motive interaction*. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 46, 183-206
- [29] Lewicki, R., Saunders, D.M. and Minton, J.M. [1997], *Essentials of Negotiation*, Irwin, Chicago, IL.
- [30] Lindner, E.G. [2006], *Emotion and Conflict: Why it is important to understand how emotions affect conflict and how conflict affects*

- emotions. In Deutsch M., Coleman T.P., Marcus E.C.[ed.] The handbook of Conflict Resolution: Theory and practice. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons Publisher – 2006
- [31] Lustig M [2006], Intercultural competence, interpersonal communication across cultures
- [32] Mack, R.W. and Snyder, R.C. [1957], The analysis of social conflict – toward an overview and synthesis, *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, Vol. 1, pp. 212-48.
- [33] Mehrabian A., [2009] *Silent Messages: Implicit Communication of Emotions and attitudes*, Wadsworth Publishing Company
- [34] Moors, A. [2010]. Theories of emotion causation. In De Houwer, J., Hermans, D., *Cognition and emotion*. Psychology Press NY.
- [35] Morley, Michael J [2010], *Managerial Psychology: Intercultural Competence*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited
- [36] Nierenberg G. [1987] *Fundamentals of Negotiating*, New York, Perennai Library
- [37] Nyklicek, I., Vingerhoets, A.J.J.M., & Zeelenberg, M. [Eds.]. [2011]. *Emotion regulation and well-being*. New York: Springer
- [38] Pease A [2006], *Body language: how to read others thoughts by their gestures*
- [39] Pondy, L.R. [1967], *Organizational conflict: concepts and models*, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 12, pp. 296-320.
- [40] Poyatos F. [1992], *Advances in non-verbal communication*
- [41] Roseman, I. J., Wiest, C., & Swartz, T. S. [1994]. Phenomenology, behaviors, and goals differentiate discrete emotions. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 67
- [42] Rubin, J.Z., Pruitt, D.G. and Kim, S.H. [1994], *Social Conflict: Escalation, Stalemate, and Settlement*, 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- [43] Saarni, C. [2011]. *Emotional Competence and Effective Negotiation: The integration of Emotion Understanding, Regulation and Communication*. In Aquilar, F., Calluccio, M. *Psychological and Political Strategies For Peace Negotiation*, Springer LLC, New York
- [44] Schmidt, S.M. and Kochan, T.A. [1972], *Conflict: toward conceptual clarity*, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 17, pp. 359-71.
- [45] Streeck, J. [2002]. *A body and its gestures*
- [46] Streek J and Knapp M.L. [1992], The interaction of visual and verbal features in human interaction. In Poyatos F. *Advances in nonverbal communication: Sociocultural, clinical, ethnic and literary perspectives*. Philadelphia
- [47] Ting-Toomey [2000], *Importance of non-verbal communication*